

Article

Recognition of Stress Activation by Unobtrusive Multi Sensing Setup

Veronica Chiara Zuccalà ^{1,2}

¹ National Research Council of Italy, Institute of Clinical Physiology, 56124 Pisa, Italy; veronica.zuccala2@unibo.it (V.C.Z.); riccardo.favilla@ifc.cnr.it (R.F.)

² Department of Electrical, Electronic, and Information Engineering “Guglielmo Marconi”, University of Bologna, 40136 Bologna, Italy

* Correspondence: giuseppe.coppini@ifc.cnr.it

Abstract: It is recognized that stress conditions play an important role in the definition of individual wellness and represent a major risk factor for most non-communicable diseases. Most studies focus on the evaluation of response to maximal stress conditions while a few of them reports results about the detection/monitoring of response to mild stimulations. In this study, we investigate the capability of some physiological signs and indicators (including Heart Rate, Heart Rate Variability, Respiratory Rate, Galvanic Skin Response) to recognize stress in response to moderate cognitive activation in daily life settings. To achieve this goal, we built up an unobtrusive platform to collect signals from healthy volunteers (10 subjects) undergoing cognitive activation via Stroop Color Word Test. We integrated our dataset with data from the Stress Recognition in the Automobile Drivers dataset. Following data harmonization, signal recordings in both datasets were split into five-minute blocks and a set of 12 features was extracted from each block. A feature selection was implemented by two complementary approaches: Sequential Forward Feature Selection (SFFS) and Auto-Encoder (AE) neural networks. Finally, we explored the use of Self-Organizing Map (SOM) to provide a flexible representation of an individual status. From the initial feature set we have determined, by SFFS analysis, that 2 of them (median Respiratory Rate and number peaks in Galvanic Skin Response signals) can discriminate activation statuses from resting ones. In addition, AE experiments also support that two features can suffice for recognition. Finally, we showed that SOM can provide a comprehensive but compact description of activation statuses allowing a fine prototypical representation of individual status.

Keywords: personal wellness; stress monitoring; multi-sensing platforms; imaging photoplethysmography; galvanic skin response; sequential forward feature selection; auto-encoder networks; self-organizing maps

Citation: Zuccalà, V.C.; Favilla, R.; Coppini, G. Recognition of Stress Activation by Unobtrusive Multi-Sensing Setup. *Appl. Sci.* **2021**, *11*, 6381. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app11146381>

Academic Editor: Alexander E. Hramov

Received: 31 May 2021

Accepted: 7 July 2021

Published: 10 July 2021

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1. Introduction

Wellness indicates the state or condition of being in good physical and mental health. According to the World Health Organization, health should be defined as a state of complete physical, mental, and social wellness, and not merely as the absence of disease and infirmity [1].

Stress is a common state of emotional strain that plays a crucial role in everyday quality of life with a significant impact on the wellness state of a person. This state consists of several complementary and interacting components (i.e., cognitive, affective, and psycho-physiological). Furthermore, chronic stress carries a wide range of health-related diseases, including cardiovascular diseases, cerebrovascular diseases, diabetes, and immune deficiencies [2,3]. Due to the adverse effects of stress in our daily life, stress monitoring and management has been receiving an increasing attention in healthcare and wellness research [4]. As a matter of fact, stress is recognized as a major risk factor for most non-communicable diseases and its evaluation is crucial for defining individual wellness.

Stress induces anomalous responses of the Autonomic Nervous Systems (ANS) which is a main actor in stress counteraction [5,6]. In particular, the activation of the sympathetic nervous system might be accompanied by many physical reactions, such as increasing the heart rate and blood supply to muscles, activating sweat glands, and increasing respiratory rate.

As to stress monitoring, several physiological signals and indicators provide important clues about individual status. Heart rate (HR) and heart rate variability (HRV) are crucial indicators of the psychophysical status of an individual and are useful clues for detecting risky conditions. The HR varies according to the body's physical needs, changes being observed in a variety of conditions including physical exercise, sleep, anxiety, stress, illness, and assumption of drugs. Monitoring the heart rate is therefore important in both normal and disease conditions. The HRV is an index of the adaptation of the heart to circumstances by detecting and readily responding to unpredictable stimuli. The HRV is mainly modulated by the sympathetic and parasympathetic components of the autonomic nervous system [7]. Beside alterations related to cardiac diseases [8], HRV is an important measure of mental stress and, coupled with the HR, is commonly used to monitor individual wellness in behavioral research [9]. The gold standard for HR and HRV assessment is ECG recording that allows the fine localization of heart beats [10]. In recent years, several methods have been studied to allow the non-contact measurement of HR and HRV, including HR from speech [11], thermal imaging [12], microwave Doppler effect [13], and imaging photoplethysmography (iPPG) [14–17]. The latter approach could greatly simplify data acquisition, making measurement easily available in non-clinical scenarios (e.g., driver monitoring [14], human–machine interaction monitoring [18]). According to our previous experience [19], iPPG can offer a valid alternative to standard PPG.

Respiratory rate (RR) carries important information on a person's health condition and physiological stability, an abnormal respiratory rate being a strong illness indicator [20]. In particular, respiratory rate increases significantly under stressful situations [21]. Current methods to collect respiration data include the use of respiration belts, measurement of impedance through ECG electrodes, spirometers, or visual observation/counting. These techniques have drawbacks that limit the frequency and convenience of the respiratory monitoring. The large diffusion of wearable devices has stimulated interest in monitoring athlete training, with the aim of maximizing performance, and minimizing the risk of injury and illness. In these field, chest belts are a common choice. It worth mentioning that respiratory rate too could be monitored by imaging ([22–24]).

Galvanic skin response (GSR) is sensitive to many different stimuli (strong emotion, a startling event, pain, exercise, deep breathing, a demanding task, cognitive workload, and stressing stimulation) and identifying the primary cause of a particular skin-conductivity response may be hard. Anyway, a lot of different studies reported that the electrodermal response represents an adequate measure for stress-related sympathetic activation [25]. GSR can be measured by different methods. In general, GSR sensor measures the real-time skin conductance which is related to the sweat gland activity depending on emotional response and environmental condition [26]. GSR is typically acquired in hand fingers.

In recent years, the interest of the scientific community has progressively expanded toward multi-sensing technologies able to integrate different signals and build effective monitoring system useful to detect dangerous conditions and driving coping actions [27]. In particular, machine learning paradigms looks very promising, and their application is an active field of investigation [28–30].

A common framework of most studies on stress detection/monitoring is the evaluation of response to maximal (or intense) stress. This provides significant details on the individual capability to react to severe stress. On the other hand, maximal activation is not the most common experience in everyday life. People usually face a wide spectrum of stressors implying a variety of activations both positive and negative.

In this work, we focus on the impact of mild stimulations which can be somehow comparable to usual conditions that everyone can deal with in daily life. The aim is to

set up a general platform useful to observe the individual status in routine setting (e.g., working in an office, driving a car) making it possible to design minimally obtrusive monitoring/testing procedures for detecting stress situations even in response to mild cognitive activation or other daily activities.

In the following we will report on the use of machine learning techniques for recognizing activation statuses with respect to resting conditions. To obtain a description of individual status, iPPG, respiratory waves and GSR signals are integrated at feature level. Our main aim is to build a flexible representation scheme able to capture the different facets of individual status, rather than implementing a rest/stress classification scheme. The reported usage of Kohonen map allows the representation of the individual status through a set of prototypes (weight vectors) learned from real data without supervision.

In next sections, after describing the used datasets (Section 2) and the related harmonization/processing methodology adopted to derive a compact feature set from signals acquired in different conditions (Section 3), we analyze the discriminating power of such a feature set (Section 4) and describe the use of the Self-Organizing Map (SOM) to represent the status of an individual (Section 5). Results are reported in Section 6.

2. Datasets

In this work we used data from two different datasets: the first one is called Mild Cognitive Activation (MCA) dataset and was collected in our laboratory to investigate stress response during cognitive activation in an office-like setting; the second one is the Stress Recognition in Automobile Drivers (SRAD) dataset from the MIT Media Lab made publicly available for scientific purposes [31].

2.1. The MCA Dataset

Ten healthy participants (7 females and 3 males with mean age 45 years, range 25–62) were recruited for voluntary participation in this study. The experimental protocol received the Ethical Clearance certification (0050349/2019) by the National Research Council Committee for Research Ethics and Bioethics. Written informed consent was obtained from all subjects. The following non-medical commercial devices were adopted to monitor physiological signals:

- IDS UI-5240SE gigabit ethernet camera with a CMOS monochrome sensor to monitor HR and HRV via face iPPG. To enhance the iPPG signal, an optical band-pass filter centered at 560 nm with a bandwidth of 40 nm was mounted on the camera.
- BioHarness 3 Zephyr chest belt used to measure RR;
- Shimmer3 GSR to acquire galvanic skin response.

All sensors were connected to an Apple Mac Mini computer (Intel Core i7 dual-core 3 GHz processor, 16 GB RAM, and 500 GB SSD).

Cognitive activation was induced by the Stroop Color Word Test (SCWT). A portable SCWT was implemented by an ad hoc Java app (Figure 1). We used two different versions of the test:

- Test A—a congruent version of the SCWT, where the font color always matched the displayed color name. A two-seconds maximum response time was adopted, the overall test lasting two minutes.
- Test B—an incongruent version of the SCWT, where the font color did not match the displayed color name. Maximal response time limits as in Test A and overall test duration was three minutes.

During the acquisition, subjects were sitting in front of a computer monitor at a distance of about one meter (see Figure 2). The camera was positioned on a tripod next the monitor. To reduce acquisition artifacts related to involuntary movements, the chair had a headrest to contain head motion and make the recording comfortable for the volunteer. Through the iPPG camera the acquisition was continuously monitored by experimenters.

Videos were permanently stored for post-processing analysis. The subject face was illuminated by a white LED light source.

Figure 1. Stroop Color Word Test.

Figure 2. Experimental setup for MCA data acquisition.

Data acquisition occurred according to the following schedule:

1. At first the volunteer was asked to fill the Perceived Stress Scale questionnaire [32]. Subsequently, all the devices were positioned and tuned.
2. The subject was asked to close his/her eyes and relax. Signals were recorded for five minutes in resting state.
3. Subsequently, signals were acquired during cognitive activation induced by the SCWT using Test A followed by Test B.

To self-assess the stress level, after each test we used two different tools as reported in [33]:

- A Likert-scaled (1–5) question directly asking subjects how much stressed they were feeling during tests [10];
- A subset of the Stress Appraisal Measure questionnaire [34] including questions 2, 16, 24, and 26.

2.2. The SRAD Dataset

SRAD database contains a collection of multi-parametric recordings from 17 healthy volunteers during driving. The dataset is fully described in [31] and is freely available for download in the Physionet repository [35] at [36]. Records include two 15-min rest periods occurred before and after a driving session, respectively. In rest periods, the volunteer sat in the garage with eyes closed and the car in idle. After the first rest period, drivers drove, for around 50 min, on a prescribed route including city streets and highways. Four types of physiological sensors were used during the experiment: electrocardiogram, electromyogram (not used in the present study), galvanic skin response, and respiration. ECG electrodes were placed in a modified lead II configuration. Respiration was monitored through chest cavity expansion using an elastic Hall-effect sensor strapped around the driver's diaphragm. The ECG was sampled at 496 Hz, the galvanic skin response and respiratory wave were sampled at 31 Hz.

3. Dataset Harmonization and Analysis

For each subject, the MCA dataset included three blocks of data. The first block was 5 min long and contained the data acquired during the rest state. The other two blocks were 2 min and 3 min long respectively and contained data acquired during activation of Test A and B, respectively. For our aims, these two blocks were merged into a single 5-min window. In this way, each record contains two 5-min blocks.

To homogenize the data from the two datasets, all SRAD recordings were divided into non-overlapping blocks lasting five minutes. For each subject we had, on average, a 3–5 blocks representing the resting condition and about 9–11 blocks for driving periods. A total of 140 blocks, 39 at rest and 101 during driving was extracted.

Signals and data of both datasets were analyzed to extract a set Y of 12 psychophysical features from ECG, video signal, RR, and GSR as summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. The set Y of extracted features and related source sensors.

Feature	Sensor	
	MCA Dataset	SRAD Dataset
Median RR	Chest belt	Chest belt
RR interquartile range	Chest belt	Chest belt
Minimum RR	Chest belt	Chest belt
Maximum RR	Chest belt	Chest belt
Number of GSR peaks	GSR	GSR
Maximum GSR peak amplitude	GSR	GSR
Median GSR peak amplitude	GSR	GSR
NN	Video iPPG	ECG
SDNN	Video iPPG	ECG
LF	Video iPPG	ECG
HF	Video iPPG	ECG
LF/HF	Video iPPG	ECG

It is worth mentioning that data from auto-evaluation questionnaires are only available for MCA and, therefore, they were not considered for data analysis. In any case, all MCA subjects did not refer relevant stressing conditions both before, during, and after test.

3.1. MCA Dataset Analysis

The video signal was processed as described in [19] to extract HR and HRV descriptors. In particular, blood volume pulses were detected by analyzing time peaks in video signals. The related time series provided the video tachogram used for HRV analysis. To remove possible artifacts, the inter beat intervals were analyzed by a variable-threshold non-causal algorithm [37]. Tachograms were analyzed both in time domain and in frequency domain. Concerning time domain, we calculated the average time between adjacent normal heartbeats (NN) and its standard deviation (SDNN). Concerning frequency do-

main, HRV description was based on power spectrum density (PSD), as estimated by the Lomb–Scargle periodogram. According to the standard definition of the HRV frequency bands, low frequency (LF) and high frequency (HF) were calculated as the area under the PSD curve corresponding from 0.04 Hz to 0.15 Hz and from 0.15 Hz to 0.4 Hz, respectively. The LF component reflects both sympathetic and parasympathetic actions, the HF component reflects parasympathetic action, and the LF/HF ratio is a measure of the sympatho/vagal balance.

The values of the median, the interquartile range, the minimum, and the maximum were calculated for the respiratory rate. RR waveforms were monitored to detect too long or too short leading to a rate outside a physiological range (8–25 bpm).

Concerning the galvanic skin response, the interfering mains frequency (50 Hz) was removed from the signal by a notch filter. Subsequently, the GSR signal was down sampled to 10 Hz. Then it was filtered through a mean filter spanning a 4 s window and a median filter spanning 8 s. To obtain the phasic component, the signal from the median filter was subtracted to the one from the mean filter. The number of peaks, the maximum peak amplitude, and the median peak value were calculated. A total of 20 blocks was then available from MCA: 10 in rest condition and 10 during SCWT.

3.2. SRAD Dataset Analysis

Due to incompleteness of data, seven SRAD subjects were excluded from the analysis, and a sub-group of 10 subjects with IDs 4, 5, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 15, and 16 was considered in this work. Only the signals common to MCA dataset were analyzed. They included: ECG, respiratory wave, and the GSR acquired on the palm of the hand. ECG signals were first pre-processed to detect QRS complexes by Pan-Tompkins algorithm [38] and derive tachograms that were processed as in the case of MCA data. The respiratory rate (breaths per minute) was estimated from the respiratory wave by detecting and counting the signal peaks. The GSR was analyzed as previously described for the MCA dataset.

We wish to point out that 13 blocks of ECG recordings (10 at rest and 3 during driving) resulted corrupted and were not included in the analysis. A total of 127 blocks was therefore available from SRAD: 29 in rest condition and 98 during driving.

4. Feature Analysis and Activation Recognition

We have analyzed the Y feature set with respect to its capabilities to recognize resting states from activation ones, particular attention being paid to the relevance of the various features. To this end we investigated two complementary approaches: Sequential Forward Feature Selection (SFFS) and Auto-Encoder (AE) neural networks.

SFFS is a well-established search algorithm whose advantages and limits are well known [39]. In particular, SFFS is known to work nicely, though non-optimally, for spaces with moderate dimension [40]. Therefore, though more sophisticated techniques exist, we adopted SFFS as reasonable trade-off between simplicity and expected accuracy.

Simple feature selection is based on the use of a possibly optimal subset of available features, and may hinder the correlation among features. During the feature selection process, dimensionality reduction is usually achieved by completely discarding some dimensions, which inevitably lead to loss of information. However, sample data in high-dimensional space generally cannot diffuse uniformly in the whole space; they actually lie in a low-dimensional manifold embedded in high-dimensional space, the dimension of the manifold being called the intrinsic dimensionality of the data [41]. Therefore, we explored an alternative approach based on AEs. They provide a sort of non-linear generalization of principal component analysis [42]. AEs are largely employed in different machine learning applications and provide a modern non-supervised framework to assess the intrinsic dimensionality of data space based on neural networks that learn to output an optimal reconstruction of the input.

Methods were implemented in MATLAB using ad hoc scripts.

4.1. Sequential Forward Feature Selection

As summarized in Algorithm 1 SFFS is an iterative search algorithm aiming to find the best subset including $K, K < n$, features of the original n -dimensional set Y according to the predefined criterion J . At first the best single feature optimizing a predefined criterion is individuated. Afterward, the same criterion is optimized using pairs of features, pairs being generated by sequentially adding to the previous best single feature one of the remaining features. The best couple of features is so defined. Next, triplets of features are formed using one of the remaining features and the previous best couple. This procedure continues until K features are found.

Algorithm 1: Sequential Forward Feature Selection

Result: Best feature subset Y_K including K features
 $Y_0 = \emptyset$;
while $i < K$ **do**
 $x^+ = \arg \max_x [J(Y + x)]$ with $x \in Y - Y_i$;
 $Y_{i+1} = Y_i + x^+$;
 $i = i + 1$;
end

The process was implemented using the MATLAB `sequentialfs` function which selects a subset of features from the data matrix that best predict the data by sequentially selecting features until there is no improvement in prediction. Prediction was implemented by Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA) [43]. For each candidate feature subset, `sequentialfs` performs 10-fold cross-validation by repeatedly training and testing a model (in our case the LDA classifier) with different training and test subsets.

As `sequentialfs` randomly splits the initial dataset to implement 10-fold cross-validation, the feature selection process can yield to different results depending on the run. This is true for both the number of selected features and which features are selected. To analyze this effect, `sequentialfs` was run 1000 times. For each run, we recorded the features selected by the procedure and the order in which they were selected. In addition, we set up a scoring system to properly weigh the relevance of the features. Specifically, at each run, every selected feature received a score equal to its position in the selection process (e.g., 1 for the first one, 3 for the third one). The features that were not selected were given a conventional score of 12. The process was repeated for every run and the scores for each run were summed up. By doing so, a final score of 1000 would indicate a feature selected as the first one in all runs. A feature with a final score of 12,000 would be a feature never selected by the method. The method was trained using the SRAD, while MCA data were used as independent test set. Related results are reported in Section 6, where the behavior of k-means clustering is also discussed.

4.2. Auto-Encoder Neural Networks

An auto-encoder neural network was applied to the SRAD dataset. This was designed as a feed-forward neural network with 12 input units, a single hidden layer with logistic activation, and an output layer with 12 units. The hidden layer had several units variable from 1 to 12.

The network was trained to reconstruct the input pattern by minimizing the *MSE* loss function using the scaled conjugate gradient descent algorithm [44] with a maximum number of epochs set to 1000.

To optimize data usage and reduce the risk of over-fitting, a training scheme based on 5-fold cross-validation. Twelve AE models were obtained, each with a different number of hidden units ranging from 1 to 12.

Using the feature sets generated by the auto-encoder, we trained a family of LDA classifiers to recognize driving periods from rest ones in the SRAD data. This process generated 12 classification models each of them using several features ranging from 1 to 12.

In Section 6, accuracy of LDA classifiers in predicting the activation level based on AE features is reported.

5. Representation of Activation Status in SOM Space

Up to now we have considered the discrimination of resting statuses from activity-related ones, a task relevant for monitoring and possibly advising a person against risky conditions. As a matter of fact, a sharp dichotomization between activation and rest is rather arbitrary and dependent on the subject. In fact, stress responses are largely variable among individuals and, for an individual, they vary with time. It is, therefore, not surprising that for a given subject, a set of feature values can relate to a possible activation status, while for another subject similar values can relate to a different condition. On the other hand, labels used for training are defined by the presence/absence of stimulation which, in general, produces a different response depending on the subject. Therefore, we decided to explore unsupervised machine learning paradigms which do not need a priori data labeling. In particular, we resorted to investigate the use of Kohonen SOM which can build accurate, but low-dimensional, topology preserving-maps of the input data space [45]. This means that similar inputs data tend to excite neighboring units in the map.

The map space is defined beforehand, usually as a finite two-dimensional region where a set of nodes m_i , $i = 1, \dots, N$ is arranged in a regular grid.

Each node is fed by input data \mathbf{x}_k via a weight vector \mathbf{w}_i . For a given input \mathbf{x}_k , the output of the network is defined by the best matching (or winning) unit m_c obtained by:

$$c = \arg \min_k (||\mathbf{w}_k - \mathbf{x}||) \quad (1)$$

The weight \mathbf{w}_c represents the network response and is a point in data space. In this way, the SOM maps the high-dimensional input space to the low-dimensional network space.

During training, nodes in the map space stay fixed, while their weight vectors are moved toward the input data without spoiling the topology induced from the map space. During a training epoch all input patterns are presented to the network. For each pattern, the weight of m_c unit and neighboring units are adapted according to a predefined neighborhood function h_{ck} (Gaussian is a common choice for h). In this work we adopted the batch version of the SOM adaptation algorithm [45] leading to the adaptation rule:

$$\mathbf{w}_i = \frac{\sum_k h_{ci} \mathbf{x}_k}{\sum_k h_{ci}} \quad (2)$$

Equation (2) ensures a faster convergence and provide more stable results with respect to stochastic adaptation. After training, SOM can build accurate topographic representation of the input space catching significant details including data clustering. In particular, each weight vector can be viewed as a prototype in data space as it tends to respond to a set of "near" input points.

Using the MATLAB Neural Network package, we have analyzed 2D maps of varying dimensions, from 3×3 to 6×6 units. Networks were trained using the SRAD dataset. The obtained maps were tested using the MCA dataset.

6. Results

Data were analyzed from different viewpoints including feature analysis and selection and their ability to describe and recognize rest from activation statuses. Given the limited sample size of MCA dataset we decide to use SRAD data as development set and MCA data as test set.

6.1. SFFS Analysis

Results of the feature selection process are summarized in Table 2 where features are ranked according to the SFFS score and selection frequency is also reported. In particular, the median RR was selected in all runs, and is constantly the most relevant single feature. This suggests that it carries a significant piece of information, irrespective of how the data are split between training and test set. The number of GSR peaks obtains the second score in the process, being selected in almost 99% of the runs.

Table 2. SFFS score and selection frequency (SF) for each feature.

Features	Score	SF (%)
Median RR	1000	100
Number of GSR peaks	2146	98.7
LF/HF	9220	34.2
RR Interquartile range	9571	30.9
NN	9842	26.2
SDNN	10,958	11.8
LF	11,501	7.0
Minimum RR	11,700	4.0
Maximum GSR peak amplitude	11,850	1.7
HF	11,974	0.5
Median GSR peak amplitude	11,991	0.1
Maximum RR	12,000	0

After the first two features, we observed a marked drop in the score. Indeed, LF/HF (the feature with the third best score, i.e., >9200) was selected in 34% of the runs only. Similar results were observed for the RR interquartile range and NN. Finally, all other features have scores that are very close to the maximum (>10,000) to end up with the last one (the maximum RR) never being selected by the process. Table 3 shows values for the two most relevant features for all subjects of SRAD used in this work. Analogous data are reported for MCA in the Table 4.

Table 3. SRAD database: Median RR and Number of GSR peaks both at rest and during driving. Interquartile range is reported in brackets.

ID	Median RR (bpm)		Number of GSR Peaks	
	Rest	Driving	Rest	Driving
04	13.5 (3)	24.5 (3)	8 (6)	22.5 (5)
05	15.5 (3)	23 (4.5)	0 (0)	21 (8.5)
07	14 (2)	20 (2)	10.5 (2)	25 (5)
08	12 (2)	20.5 (2)	0 (2.25)	17 (7)
09	15 (0.75)	21 (2)	0 (0)	15.5 (3)
10	13 (0)	20 (3.8)	3 (0)	18 (6.75)
11	16 (1)	21 (3.3)	0 (0)	21 (5.5)
12	18 (0)	24 (1.6)	6 (6)	26 (10.25)
15	14 (3)	17 (2)	5 (12)	18 (1.5)
16	18 (0.75)	24.5 (2)	15 (8.25)	31 (4)

Table 4. MCA database: Median RR with interquartile range (in brackets) together with the Number of GSR peaks both at rest and during SCWT. No IQR is available for MCA GSR as only one block is present in data.

ID	Median RR (bpm)		Number of GSR Peaks	
	Rest	SCWT	Rest	SCWT
01	14 (1)	17.3 (2.7)	0	25
02	16 (3)	17 (1.5)	0	19
03	16 (2)	19.5 (2)	0	18
04	13 (2)	13.5 (1)	0	32
05	11 (4)	18 (3.5)	0	25
06	10 (2)	14.5 (4.5)	11	45
07	17 (1)	19.5 (1)	7	36
08	15 (1)	17 (0)	0	0
09	13 (1)	15.5 (1)	0	0
10	13 (1)	13 (2)	5	44

In Figure 3 we plot the accuracy of LDA classifier obtained on the SRAD dataset with different numbers of features according to SFFS ranking. A similar plot is also given for MCA as test set. For SRAD the accuracy amounts at about 93% for a single feature rising to about 98% with two features with no further significant changes using the remaining features. For the MCA data we observe a rapid increase to about 90% with two features, fluctuations being present when using more than six features.

Figure 3. On the **left**: Accuracy of LDA classifier evaluated on the SRAD dataset varying the number of features according to SFFS ranking. On the **right**: accuracy versus number of features evaluated on MCA.

6.2. AE Features

In general, the observed accuracy of AE features resulted high (>90%), with the worst performance (about 93%) obtained when a single feature was available (Figure 4). When two (or more) features were employed, the accuracy fluctuated around 93–95%. Therefore using more than two AE features did not significantly improve discrimination capabilities. Indeed, a maximal accuracy of (about 95%) was already met using two features.

Figure 4. On the left: Accuracy of LDA classifier evaluated on the SRAD dataset with different auto-encoding dimensionality. On the right: accuracy evaluated on MCA.

When each of the 12 models were tested on the MCA dataset, results were found to be affected by a larger variability (Figure 4). With a single feature, the accuracy is 0.5 (chance level). However, also in this case, using two features produces a substantial accuracy boosting. This reached its maximum with three features (at around 90%). The inclusion of additional features results in accuracy fluctuation about lower values.

To sum up, both SFFS and AE support the finding that two features may be sufficient to reliably recognize activation statuses.

6.3. Data Clustering

According to the results of the selection process, the best features were identified as the median RR and the number of GSR peaks. We have further investigated the joint use of these features with respect to their capability to cluster the data space. To this end, we partitioned SRAD data in two cluster using standard k-means algorithm as provided in MATLAB. Clustering (see Figure 5) was correlated with the dataset labels (either rest or driving). K-means clustering led to an 87.9% recognition rate for the rest state and a 92.3% recognition rate for the driving state. As shown in Table 5, the overall classification accuracy was 89.4%.

It is worth mentioning that using the same cluster centroids for MCA data we found a 90% rate of correct classification (Figure 5). By taking a closer look at these results, we found that 100% classification accuracy was not achieved as the algorithm failed to recognize the activation state of the two non-naïve subjects. Actually, they have had significant previous experience with the SCWT.

Table 5. Confusion matrices for k-means clustering for both SRAD and MCA datasets (R: rest, A: activation).

		Predicted as				
		SRAD		MCA		
True	R	48 (92.3%)	12 (12.1%)	R	10 (100%)	2 (20%)
	A	4 (7.7%)	87 (87.9%)	A	0 (0%)	8 (80%)

Figure 5. On the **left**: cluster scatter-plot on the SRAD dataset. On the **right**: clustering evaluated on MCA.

To better understand what could have been the contribution of additional features, we repeated the same process using other features. However, performance of k-means clustering deviated significantly from rest/activation data labeling.

Finally, we wish to point out that k-means was repeated 1000 times with random cluster initialization: we observed changes in final centroid position in less than 15% of cases. However, even in these cases, displacement of cluster centroids was quite limited. Indeed, we observed a change in coordinates of $< 1\%$ the total range of the feature space.

6.4. Self-Organizing Maps

We have trained a set of two-dimensional SOMs with several units varying from 3×3 to 6×6 . We did not consider larger maps due the limited dataset size. Maps were trained on the SRAD dataset. For each map size, training was run ten times with random weight initialization. Apart changes in map orientation, no relevant difference was detected inside each run.

As we are interested in the topographic representation produced by SOMs, we have analyzed each map with respect to the distance between weights of neighboring units (the so-called U-map), and the distribution in the network space of each weight dimension (weight-plane maps). In addition, to explore the semantic role of unit activation we analyzed the distribution of data labels in network space (categorical hit maps). Since the results do not vary significantly with the number of units, to ease readability, we show only data for 5×5 SOM.

Map distances in Figure 6 suggest that the units in the right upper corner are rather apart from the other units that tend to be closer each other. This confirms previous data from feature selection and data clustering, and suggests that the data space can be partitioned into two highly structured clusters. It is worth noting that larger maps are expected to capture finer structural details of data as suggested by the comparison of the maps.

Figure 6. Maps of distances between the weight of neighboring units for 5×5 SOM. Darkest colors indicate largest distance while light colors denote smallest ones.

The distribution of SOM weights (Figure 7) provides additional support to distance maps. In particular, spatial arrangement of weights looks consistent among different map sizes. In addition, several components (e.g., those corresponding to median RR, GSR peak number, LF/HF, NN, LF, and HF) exhibit a well-defined spatial distribution. In particular, some of them such as the weights of median RR and GSR peak number can be related to the partition appearing the left upper part of the map.

Categorical hit maps (top of Figure 8) for the rest and activation labels of the SRAD dataset show a rather neat distinction among the two categories: only a few units respond simultaneously to both rest and activation data. In the bottom part of Figure 8, we report the hit maps for rest and activation categories of MCA dataset. These maps exhibit a behavior similar to the case of SRAD data.

Map units can be a posteriori labeled according to several criteria. For example, using the majority-voting scheme as in [46], we obtain the label map in Figure 9. Comparing MCA hits maps with labels we obtain 3 misclassifications (2 false rests and one false activation). It is worth noting that misclassified patterns are next to units that would correctly classify them. It stands to reason that using larger maps trained on extended data could improve labeling result. On the other hand, majority-voting labeling can be sub-optimal and the use of fuzzy labeling [47] should be preferred.

Figure 7. Maps of weight components. Darkest colors indicate smallest values while light colors denote largest ones.

Figure 8. Map of winning units according to rest and activation labels. Top: data from SRAD dataset, Bottom: data for MCA dataset.

Figure 9. SOM units labeled according to a majority-voting scheme described in [46].

To summarize, results support that SOM has learned a topographic representation of the input space congruous with *a priori* data labels.

7. Discussion and Conclusions

In this work we reported on the use of a measurement setup aiming to the unobtrusive monitoring of psychophysical signals for detecting and analyzing potential stressing conditions in everyday life settings.

We have jointly analyzed two different datasets (MCA collected by our research group and SRAD from MIT Media lab). Aiming to assess stress activation, both were produced by recording a set of physiological signals in different settings. Our investigation was mainly conducted using the SRAD dataset (the most numerous) as development set, while MCA data were used for independent testing.

The work is focused on two main aspects: (a) recognition of activation statuses from resting ones and (b) building a comprehensive but compact description of individual status that could be useful in monitoring individual well-being.

From the original data space we extracted a set of 12 features including descriptors of HR, HRV, RR and GSR which are sensitive to individual response to stressors with emphasis on ANS response. Analysis of SRAD feature space by SFFS supports the conclusion that median RR and GSR peaks number has a prominent discriminating power and can lead to recognize activation statuses, which is also confirmed by MCA data analysis.

We also tested AE features obtained from the SRAD dataset. They are estimated using whole original data and are expected to reduce the potential information loss of SFFS mechanism. Results suggest that using two AE features can lead to good discrimination of rest states from activation ones. A similar conclusion is obtained using the same AE features for MCA dataset. It stands to reason that our data space is intrinsically two-dimensional with respect recognition of activation condition. This conclusion is also in accord with SFFS results.

Though the obtained results are consistent with background literature, they are in a sense surprising as the two datasets used for development and testing were acquired under completely different experimental conditions (while driving or while performing the SCWT). This supports the idea that the used feature set is highly descriptive of individual activation status and able to predict a wide spectrum of activation conditions. When applying standard k-means algorithm using the two most relevant features we observed two clusters that well represent rest and activation labels. This clustering is consistent with MCA data.

It must be pointed out that individual responses are intrinsically variable and the use of flexible but compact representations of individual status are highly desirable. In this context, the use of SOM networks revealed promising.

Being non-supervised, SOM can autonomously discover significant pieces of information embedded in data space. In addition, they project input data manifold onto network space by preserving topology and related structural properties such as clustering.

SOMs derived on SRAD data show the existence of two virtually separated zones in the map: one of them tends to respond to rest statuses, while the other best matches activation statuses. After labeling the SOM with a majority-voting scheme, we correctly classified 85% of MCA data blocks, as compared to 90% by k-means clustering with SFFS. SOM activation maps show that misclassification occurred next the border between the two groups. It is expected that using fuzzy labeling schemes along with extended training and testing data can lead to performance improvement.

A significant aspect of SOMs that is relevant for applications is their ability to discover and represent the internal structure of large clusters. In particular, each map unit can be viewed as a prototype (or code) of the individual's status. In this view, activation (or rest) of a person is naturally represented by a structured family of codes. Investigation of the structure of such codes is our current focus of research. It will drive the acquisition of novel data and implementation of alternative SOM labeling.

Author Contributions: Conceptualization, V.C.Z. and G.C.; Investigation, V.C.Z.; Methodology, V.C.Z., R.F. and G.C.; Supervision, G.C.; Validation, R.F., V.C.Z. and G.C.; Writing—original draft, V.C.Z.; Writing—review and editing, V.C.Z., R.F. and G.C. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding: This research received no external funding.

Institutional Review Board Statement: The study was approved by the National Research Council Committee for Research Ethics and Bioethics (Ethical Clearance certification (0050349/2019)).

Informed Consent Statement: Written informed consent was obtained from all subjects involved in the acquisition of MCA dataset to publish this paper. The Stress Recognition in Automobile Drivers dataset is made publicly by owners as is.

Data Availability Statement: The Stress Recognition in Automobile Drivers used in this study is publicly available at <https://physionet.org/content/drivedb/1.0.0/> (accessed on 7 July 2021). MCA data are not publicly available for internal policy.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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